

Supervised Contrastive Learning and Classification using LLM-Generated Synthetic Data for Medical LLM Safety

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Abstract

The increasing deployment of large language models (LLMs) in healthcare applications has increased the need for reliable methods to assess the safety and guideline consistency of synthetically generated medical statements. In this work, we propose a clinical guideline-anchored pipeline for detecting guideline-unaligned LLM outputs, with a particular focus on treatment (remdesivir) recommendations for COVID-19 whose correctness depends on adherence to authoritative medical guidance. The pipeline is comprised of automated extraction of disease-treatment specific clinical guidelines, retrieval-augmented generative summaries of treatment recommendations, generation of semantically consistent safe paraphrases and their corresponding unsafe variants. These synthetically generated data are then used for a supervised contrastive learning objective applied to biomedical transformer encoders, thus creating embedding spaces optimized to distinguish guideline-consistent (safe) from guideline-inconsistent (unsafe) statements. A downstream classifier trained on these representations is evaluated on both in-distribution (GPT-4o-mini) and out-of-distribution (DeepSeek) LLM outputs derived from synthetic and expert-validated labels.

Across all metrics, contrastively fine-tuned encoders substantially outperform their baseline counterparts. Average improvements ranging from 0.12 to 0.26 in F1 score are observed across the datasets, with similar gains in AUC, average precision, and balanced accuracy. Difficulty-stratified test results further demonstrate increased detection performance of clinically subtle unsafe variants. These findings indicate that clinical guideline-aware contrastive representation learning provides an effective and lightweight method for the safety assessment of medical LLM outputs.

Keywords: Large language models; Medical AI safety; Contrastive learning; Clinical guideline adherence; Biomedical NLP; Machine learning; Contrastive learning

1 Introduction

In recent years, the safety of large language models (LLMs) applied to medical and healthcare-related tasks have been widely studied in both research and real-world settings. Healthcare-related domains are a natural application for LLMs due to their advantages in textual and knowledge-oriented tasks [36]. These applications include, but are not limited to: medical research, triage and diagnostic assistance, education, and patient record summarization and analysis [29, 8, 2, 23]. One recent example of this was the development of the GatorTron by the University of Florida in collaboration with the NVIDIA Corporation, which was created to assist with clinical trials, large-scale data mining, medical research, and diagnostic support [37]. Commercial offerings likewise provide customized LLM-based tools for biomedical question answering, clinical note summarization, and related healthcare applications [38].

However, the adoption of LLMs in healthcare settings has raised significant concerns regarding their reliability, safety, and alignment with medical standards. LLMs may generate incorrect, outdated, or clinically substandard information—including inaccurate treatment recommendations—posing risks in clinical decision-making contexts [19, 6]. Such errors may stem from insufficient domain-specific data, poor prompting strategies, or even malicious model interference such as training data-poisoning attacks [4, 11, 32]. In safety-critical applications, even small deviations from established clinical guidelines (e.g., incorrect eligibility criteria, dosing schedules, contraindications, or evidence levels) may lead to harmful or misleading recommendations. Ensuring alignment of LLM-generated text with authoritative guidelines (e.g., CDC, NIH, IDSA, NICE) is therefore essential for responsible deployment.

Existing work on medical LLM safety has primarily focused on hallucination detection, fact-checking pipelines, and misinformation identification. While these methods help flag broadly harmful content, relatively few studies directly evaluate whether LLM-generated treatment recommendations adhere to narrow, authoritative clinical guidelines. Furthermore, prior research rarely leverages publicly accessible guideline content as structured training data to classify clinically valid from clinically invalid statements. This gap motivates the development of methods capable of detecting guideline-inconsistent therapeutic statements.

To address this gap, we introduce a proof-of-concept supervised classification pipeline for detecting unsafe (i.e., guideline-misaligned) LLM-generated medical statements. Most importantly, we examine the application of contrastive learning with LLM-based synthetic data to improve the classification task. Our pipeline first constructs an assumed canonical set of clinical guideline sentences using retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) on scraped medical guideline text. A lightweight LLM then generates paraphrases of safe statements as well as systematically distorted unsafe variants. Biomedical transformer encoders are fine-tuned using a pairwise contrastive objective to enforce embedding separation between safe and unsafe statements.

A downstream supervised classifier is trained on in-distribution (GPT-4o) embeddings and evaluated on both in-distribution and out-of-distribution (DeepSeek) unsafe embeddings to assess robustness. Because naturally occurring guideline-inconsistent statements by LLMs are difficult to obtain at scale, we demonstrate the pipeline using several synthetic datasets focused on remdesivir treatment for COVID-19.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- **Dataset creation:** We systematically construct four synthetic datasets—fully synthetic (2) and healthcare practitioner-verified (HCP) (2)—of safe and unsafe medical statements related to COVID-19 and remdesivir, organized into semantically consistent families.
- **Safety-aware embedding learning:** We fine-tune biomedical transformer encoders using a pairwise contrastive objective to enhance separability between safe and unsafe medical statements.
- **Cross-LLM evaluation:** We compare baseline and contrastively fine-tuned embedding models using both in-distribution (GPT-4o) and out-of-distribution (DeepSeek) unsafe statements for purely synthetic data and healthcare professional augmented synthetic data.
- **Practical demonstration:** We show that contrastive learning significantly improves detection of unsafe clinical statements and reduces performance degradation under cross-model shifts.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews prior work in medical LLMs, medical safety evaluation, synthetic data generation, and contrastive learning. Section 3 details our methodology, including pipeline design and experimental procedures. Section 4 presents results, and Section 5 concludes the paper. Section 6 contains references.

2 Related Work

2.1 LLMs and NLP in Medicine

Large language models have increasingly been applied to biomedical, clinical, and general medical tasks, driven by their strengths in text summarization, information retrieval, and medical question answering (QA). Prior to LLMs, NLP methods such as BERT and its biomedical variants (PubMedBERT, BioBERT, BioClinicalBERT, ClinicalBERT) were widely used for tasks such as named entity recognition (NER), relation extraction, and clinical concept linking [16, 21, 5, 18]. More recently, fine-tuned LLMs such as Med-PaLM have achieved near-expert performance on standardized medical examinations [35]. Both open-source and commercial systems now integrate LLMs into diagnostic assistance and clinical decision-support applications [1, 30]. Still, concerns regarding LLM reliability, correctness, and safety continue to be documented, warranting further investigation.

2.2 Medical LLM Safety, Fact-Checking, and Guideline Adherence

A substantial body of research focuses on reducing LLM hallucinations, improving factuality, and aligning LLM outputs with safety constraints or 'guardrails'. Methods include retrieval-augmented verification, domain-specific fine-tuning, and knowledge graph-based fact-checking [17, 34, 22]. Some studies apply these methods to medical tasks, such as using biomedical knowledge graphs combined with NER to detect safety violations in poisoned LLMs [4, 9], or combining RAG, summarization, prompt engineering, and ML classification for verification pipelines [7, 3]. Traditional supervised classification approaches have also been used for correctness prediction [27, 31, 15].

However, relatively few studies evaluate LLMs against formal clinical guidelines (NIH, CDC, NICE), and most work treats medical safety as a generic fact-checking problem rather than a guideline-consistency task. Guideline sets for many diseases are small, making heavyweight methods (e.g., knowledge graphs, full LLM fine-tuning) unnecessarily costly for narrow tasks. In fact, this narrow objective lends itself to more simple, traditional classifiers such as logistic regression trained for a specific NLP task. Currently, only limited research investigates whether clinical guidelines can be used to construct datasets or embedding spaces optimized specifically for detecting guideline-inconsistent treatment statements [28].

2.3 Synthetic Clinical Text and Guideline-Based Data Generation

Due to the limited availability of open medical data and the rising demand for large datasets in artificial intelligence and machine learning workflows, synthetic clinical text has become increasingly common. Existing work spans GANs, LLMs, VAEs, diffusion models, and probabilistic approaches for generating EHR notes, QA datasets, and adversarial scenarios [12, 33, 14, 26, 20, 13]. Some studies incorporate synthetic LLM-generated text into fact-checking pipelines, but none to our knowledge have created structured safe-unsafe contrastive families for guideline alignment detection in medical LLMs [39]. Our approach uses a systematic process: generating paraphrased safe variants and their unsafe distortions to build training pairs grounded in official clinical guidelines.

2.4 Contrastive Learning for Biomedical Embeddings

Contrastive learning methods such as SimCSE, Siamese networks, and task-specific contrastive finetuning have shown strong performance in biomedical embedding tasks [10, 25, 24]. However, existing approaches are not guideline-aware and do not use guideline-based safe-unsafe pairs. Most rely on in-batch negatives, whereas our pipeline uses explicit pairing to construct a clinically meaningful embedding space optimized for discrimination between safe and unsafe statements [40].

2.5 Summary of Literature Gaps

Overall, while prior research examines hallucination, factual accuracy, and general medical LLM safety, little work has focused on: (1) clinical guideline-based detection of unsafe treatment recommendations, (2) structured synthetic safe/unsafe statement generation within guideline families, and (3) contrastive learning optimized for guideline consistency. Our work addresses these gaps by integrating clinical guideline-derived corpus construction from public web sources, synthetic statement generation, supervised contrastive learning, and downstream safety classification within a unified pipeline.

3 Methodology

3.1 Pipeline Overview

In this study, we evaluate the effectiveness of a classification pipeline designed to detect LLM-generated statements that are misaligned with clinical guidelines. The pipeline consists of six components: (1) clinical guideline web scraping for a specified disease domain, (2) retrieval-augmented summarization of treatment guidelines for a specific treatment, (3) paraphrase generation from the summarized guideline set, (4) generation of unsafe variants, (5) contrastive learning using biomedical BERT encoders, and (6) supervised classification of safe vs. unsafe statements. Figure 1 illustrates the overall pipeline structure.

3.2 Dataset Construction

3.2.1 Clinical Guideline Extraction and Retrieval-Augmented Generation

We constructed a corpus of authoritative guideline statements by web scraping publicly available COVID-19 treatment guidelines. Our sources were the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA), National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), and the National Institutes of Health (NIH). In practical deployments, the scraper should be executed at regular intervals (e.g., triggered by webpage updates, scheduled refresh, or manual activation) to maintain alignment with evolving guidelines. Additionally, the user (e.g., healthcare practitioner, expert, etc.) should manually specify or verify the summarized guidelines.

Extracted webpage text was stored in `.txt` format. Each document was chunked and embedded using OpenAI’s `text-embedding-3-small` model. We then applied GPT-4o-mini via retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to summarize each treatment-relevant guideline cluster. Each canonical guideline sentence was assigned a universally unique identifier (UUID) referred to as the *guideline family ID*.

Duplicate or near-duplicate sentences (detected via identical family IDs or cosine similarity greater than 0.925) were removed. Non-clinical statements—such as cost-effectiveness, reimbursement, or administrative content—were automatically filtered out via keyword heuristics. For this study, we focused on the remdesivir COVID-19 treatment, yielding a final set of 17 canonical clinical guideline statements.

Fig. 1 Visual overview of the six-stage pipeline for detecting guideline-inconsistent LLM-generated clinical statements.

3.2.2 Safe Paraphrase and Unsafe Variant Generation

To simulate linguistic variability, we generated 20 paraphrases for each canonical guideline using GPT-4o-mini, yielding a total of 340 safe paraphrases. These paraphrases maintained semantic and factual equivalence with the original guideline content.

Unsafe variants were generated using the paraphrased guideline sentences. Five unsafe variants were generated per safe paraphrase, yielding a total of 1700 unsafe variants. They were produced by intentionally modifying key eligibility criteria, drug indications, limitations, or contextual qualifiers. For the training dataset, GPT-4o-mini was prompted to generate three difficulty tiers:

- **Easy:** Direct logical inversion (e.g., changing “recommended” to “not recommended”).
- **Medium:** Removal or alteration of essential clinical qualifiers.
- **Hard:** Slight factual distortions that preserve fluency while introducing subtle inconsistency.

These three tiers produce a diverse set of incorrect statements, allowing downstream models to learn fine-grained distinctions between clinically valid and invalid guideline-derived text.

3.2.3 HCP Verification of Canonical Statements

To obtain more robust results, we created separate testing data where canonical guidelines were deterministically corrupted from assumed safe to unsafe, verified by a licensed healthcare practitioner (HCP), then used to generate a small number of synthetic paraphrases. First, safe statements were altered using deterministic logic contained in regular expressions with structured corruption following several patterns:

- **Flip Recommendation:** Direct logical inversion (e.g., changing “recommended” to “not recommended”).
- **Omit Conditional:** Removal of essential clinical qualifiers (e.g., “except”, “unless”, “only when”).
- **Numeric Drift:** Alter numeric in the statement or sentence (e.g., change 7 to 10).
- **Swap care settings:** Swap or invert care settings (e.g., changing “inpatient” to “outpatient”).

Both the assumed-safe canonical statements and their deterministically corrupted unsafe counterparts were independently reviewed by the HCP and labeled as safe or unsafe given the information contained in the associated guideline sources. The HCP reviewed the statements with knowledge of synthetic or assumed labels. Statements for which the HCP disagreed with the assumed or synthetic label, or deemed the statement ambiguous or context-dependent beyond the provided information, were excluded from further analysis. The HCP was encouraged to leave notes that describe the determinations as needed, as well as instances where statements agreed with source texts but could possibly be unsafe given certain contexts. The remaining set of HCP-verified safe and unsafe statements was subsequently used as a seed corpus for evaluation, including the generation of paraphrased variants for both in-distribution and out-of-distribution testing.

3.3 Embedding Model Training

We evaluated four biomedical transformer encoders: BioMedicalBERT, ClinicalBERT, PubMedBERT, and BlueBERT. For each model, we trained (1) a baseline sentence encoder with mean pooling and (2) a contrastively fine-tuned encoder.

3.3.1 Contrastive Pair Construction

Positive (safe–safe) and negative (safe–unsafe) training pairs were constructed within each guideline family. Each unsafe variant was paired with five randomly sampled safe paraphrases from the same family, producing a controlled set of clinically meaningful contrastive pairs.

3.3.2 Training Objective

Contrastive training used PyTorch’s `CosineSimilarityLoss`, defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}(u, v, y) = \begin{cases} 1 - \cos(u, v), & y = 1 \\ \max(0, \cos(u, v) + 1), & y = -1, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $y = 1$ for positive (safe–safe) pairs and $y = -1$ for negative (safe–unsafe) pairs. Cosine similarity is defined as:

$$\cos(u, v) = \frac{u \cdot v}{\|u\| \|v\|}, \quad (2)$$

where $u \cdot v$ denotes the dot product and $\|u\|$, $\|v\|$ are vector magnitudes.

3.3.3 Model Architecture and Hyperparameters

All models used mean pooling, a 768-dimensional projection layer with `tanh` activation, and L2 normalization. Training used AdamW with a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} , a cosine warmup schedule, batch size 16, and 5 epochs. Fixed random seeds ensured reproducibility.

3.4 Classifier Training

For each embedding model, every sentence was encoded into a 768-dimensional vector. Features were standardized with `StandardScaler`. We trained a logistic regression classifier with balanced class weights on the GPT-4o-mini in-distribution dataset.

To select a decision threshold, we performed 5-fold stratified cross-validation, maximizing the F1 score, defined as:

$$\text{F1} = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}, \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, \quad \text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \quad (4)$$

3.5 Evaluation Protocol

We evaluate model performance using four standard classification metrics: Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC), Average Precision (AP), F1 score, and Balanced Accuracy (BA). For difficulty-stratified evaluation (easy, medium, hard negative variants), we additionally report the Accuracy Score (Acc).

AUC measures the probability that a randomly chosen positive instance is assigned a higher score than a randomly chosen negative instance. Formally, if $s(x)$ denotes the classifier score:

$$\text{AUC} = \Pr(s(x^+) > s(x^-)). \quad (5)$$

Average Precision (AP), the area under the precision–recall curve, is computed as the weighted mean of precisions at each threshold:

$$\text{AP} = \sum_n (R_n - R_{n-1}) P_n, \quad (6)$$

where P_n and R_n represent precision and recall at the n -th threshold.

Balanced Accuracy accounts for label imbalance and is defined as the arithmetic mean of sensitivity and specificity:

$$\text{BA} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN} + \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \right). \quad (7)$$

For category-specific (easy/medium/hard) evaluation, we also report Accuracy, defined as:

$$\text{Acc} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}. \quad (8)$$

The F1 score and its associated precision and recall formulas are provided in Section III-D.

For in-distribution (ID) evaluation, classifiers were tested on held-out GPT-4o-mini safe paraphrases and unsafe variants. This setup avoids trivial memorization and measures robustness to phrasing variation. Out-of-distribution (OOD) evaluation used DeepSeek-generated safe and unsafe statements, enabling assessment of resilience to cross-model lexical shifts and generative differences.

3.6 Hardware and Software Environment

All experiments were performed on a local machine running Ubuntu 25.04, with a 16-core AMD Ryzen 7 5800X CPU, 31.3 GiB RAM, and an AMD Radeon RX 6600 XT GPU. Synthetic text was generated using GPT-4o-mini and DeepSeek APIs. Model training used PyTorch 2.2.0 and SentenceTransformers 2.7.0. Data processing utilized Python 3.11, NumPy, Pandas, scikit-learn, and Matplotlib.

Contrastive fine-tuning and classification were executed on a single machine without distributed training. End-to-end runtime per encoder ranged from several minutes for baseline embedding models to approximately three to four hours those with contrastive fine-tuning.

4 Results

4.1 Classification Performance

Across all metrics (AUC, AP, F1, BalAcc) and embedding models (BioClinicalBERT, ClinicalBERT, PubMedBERT, and BlueBERT), contrastive learning substantially improves classification performance for in-distribution, out-of-distribution, and HCP-verified evaluations. This improvement is expected, as the embedding models are fine-tuned for a relatively narrow classification task with three types of unsafe responses defined.

On average, contrastive learning improves F1 from 0.657 to 0.920 ($\Delta = 0.263$) on the ID dataset and from 0.476 to 0.721 ($\Delta = 0.245$) on the OOD dataset. For AUC, the average increases from 0.916 to 0.963 on ID ($\Delta = 0.047$) and from 0.808 to 0.831 on OOD ($\Delta = 0.023$). Average Precision (AP) improves from 0.631 to 0.933 on ID ($\Delta = 0.302$) and from 0.416 to 0.691 on OOD ($\Delta = 0.275$). Balanced Accuracy similarly increases from 0.841 to 0.943 on ID ($\Delta = 0.102$) and from 0.703 to 0.808 on OOD ($\Delta = 0.105$).

Performance gains persist on the HCP-verified datasets. Average F1 increases from 0.661 to 0.795 ($\Delta = 0.134$) on the HCP (GPT paraphrases) dataset and from 0.610

to 0.725 ($\Delta = 0.115$) on the HCP-OOD (DeepSeek paraphrases) dataset, indicating that contrastive fine-tuning improves alignment with expert-verified safety judgments even under cross-model distribution shift.

Table 1 Performance of baseline and contrastively tuned biomedical encoders. Metrics reported for In-Distribution (ID), Out-of-Distribution (OOD), and HCP-Verified datasets. Classifier: Logistic Regression.

Model (Encoder)	AUC	AP	F1	BalAcc
<i>ID (GPT-4o-mini)</i>				
BioClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.913	0.624	0.648	0.841
ClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.894	0.577	0.610	0.817
PubMedBERT (baseline)	0.947	0.723	0.725	0.872
BlueBERT (baseline)	0.910	0.599	0.645	0.833
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	0.964	0.929	0.904	0.931
ClinicalBERT (CL)	0.949	0.930	0.913	0.933
PubMedBERT (CL)	0.966	0.941	0.938	0.960
BlueBERT (CL)	0.972	0.930	0.925	0.949
<i>OOD (DeepSeek)</i>				
BioClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.812	0.429	0.488	0.726
ClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.772	0.353	0.452	0.692
PubMedBERT (baseline)	0.851	0.484	0.530	0.728
BlueBERT (baseline)	0.798	0.397	0.433	0.667
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	0.799	0.650	0.675	0.773
ClinicalBERT (CL)	0.809	0.663	0.695	0.789
PubMedBERT (CL)	0.872	0.752	0.785	0.854
BlueBERT (CL)	0.844	0.700	0.729	0.817
<i>HCP (HCP-Verified, GPT Paraphrases)</i>				
BioClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.673	0.647	0.650	0.637
ClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.682	0.664	0.650	0.650
PubMedBERT (baseline)	0.694	0.654	0.707	0.699
BlueBERT (baseline)	0.672	0.620	0.635	0.636
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	0.828	0.884	0.776	0.811
ClinicalBERT (CL)	0.837	0.880	0.761	0.800
PubMedBERT (CL)	0.814	0.868	0.815	0.832
BlueBERT (CL)	0.882	0.915	0.826	0.847
<i>HCP-OOD (HCP-Verified, DeepSeek Paraphrases)</i>				
BioClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.666	0.635	0.635	0.627
ClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.683	0.683	0.625	0.643
PubMedBERT (baseline)	0.659	0.644	0.598	0.625
BlueBERT (baseline)	0.630	0.609	0.582	0.602
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	0.770	0.838	0.696	0.763
ClinicalBERT (CL)	0.817	0.870	0.719	0.777
PubMedBERT (CL)	0.797	0.854	0.760	0.798
BlueBERT (CL)	0.796	0.860	0.725	0.777

4.2 Embedding Space Visualization (t-SNE)

For both the ID, OOD, and HCP-verified datasets, we utilize 2-dimensional t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) plots to qualitatively assess the effect of contrastive fine-tuning. The visualized embeddings from the baseline and fine-tuned BioClinicalBERT embedding model can be found Figure 2.

Across the datasets, the t-SNE visualizations reveal clearer separation between safe and unsafe texts after contrastive learning. The ID projections show especially distinct clustering, consistent with the strong quantitative gains observed in F1, AP, and balanced accuracy. In contrast, the OOD projections exhibit more overlap between classes, but still demonstrate a far improved structure relative to baseline embeddings. This is expected due to the increased lexical and stylistic variation introduced by DeepSeek. A similar pattern emerged for the HCP-verified datasets as well, as overall performance separation improved, but not to the extent of the original ID or OOD datasets. Again, this result is expected. The source (i.e., pre-paraphrase) unsafe statements are deterministically altered, avoiding the early introduction of the subtle linguistic styles of GPT-4o or DeepSeek. In turn, this makes it more difficult for the purely GPT-4o trained BioClinicalBERT to separate the unsafe and safe statement embeddings.

(a) t-SNE (2D) projection of GPT-4o test embeddings, baseline BioClinicalBERT

(b) t-SNE (2D) projection of GPT-4o test embeddings, CL fine-tuned BioClinicalBERT

(c) t-SNE (2D) projection of DeepSeek test embeddings, baseline BioClinicalBERT

(d) t-SNE (2D) projection of DeepSeek test embeddings, CL fine-tuned BioClinicalBERT

(e) t-SNE (2D) projection of HCP-verified GPT-4o test embeddings, baseline BioClinicalBERT

(f) t-SNE (2D) projection of HCP-verified GPT-4o test embeddings, CL fine-tuned BioClinicalBERT

(g) t-SNE (2D) projection of HCP-verified Deepseek test embeddings, baseline BioClinicalBERT

(h) t-SNE (2D) projection of HCP-verified Deepseek test embeddings, CL fine-tuned BioClinicalBERT

Fig. 2 2D t-SNE visualizations of safe vs. unsafe embeddings from BioClinicalBERT for In-Distribution (GPT-4o-mini), Out-of-Distribution (DeepSeek), and HCP-verified datasets.

4.3 Difficulty-Stratified Classification Results

When segmented by difficulty, we observe that the embedding models generally perform well for classifying unsafe statements for both the baseline and contrastively fine-tuned embedding models. Note that the accuracy for each baseline embedding model differs significantly from their respective F1 scores, which is likely due to the ID and OOD datasets being imbalanced, with multiple unsafe variants generated for each safe paraphrase.

Overall, the results in Table 2 are consistent with previously shown findings that contrastive learning greatly increases predictive accuracy across all difficulty levels of unsafe statements. Average accuracy for the *Easy* category increased from 0.846 (baseline average across models) to 0.995 ($\Delta = 0.149$) after contrastive learning on the ID dataset, and from 0.844 to 0.994 ($\Delta = 0.150$) on the OOD dataset. Similarly, *Medium*-difficulty examples saw increases from 0.916 to 0.994 on the ID dataset ($\Delta = 0.078$) and from 0.843 to 0.967 for the OOD dataset ($\Delta = 0.123$). The *Hard* category improved from 0.833 to 0.980 for the ID dataset ($\Delta = 0.147$) and from 0.803 to 0.958 for the OOD dataset ($\Delta = 0.155$). Based on these aggregate results, it is clear that when the difficulty of the unsafe example increases (e.g., medium to hard), there is a greater the magnitude of improvement attributable to contrastive learning.

Table 2 Unsafe detection accuracy for logistic regression classifier. Metrics reported for baseline and contrastively (CL) fine-tuned encoders, as well as In-Distribution (ID), Out-of-Distribution (OOD), and HCP-Verified (HCP) datasets.

Model (Encoder)	Easy	Med	Hard
<i>ID (GPT-4o-mini)</i>			
BioClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.837	0.908	0.821
ClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.791	0.896	0.822
PubMedBERT (baseline)	0.915	0.951	0.849
BlueBERT (baseline)	0.841	0.908	0.838
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	0.991	0.992	0.981
ClinicalBERT (CL)	0.999	0.994	0.984
PubMedBERT (CL)	0.996	0.994	0.979
BlueBERT (CL)	0.995	0.995	0.976
<i>OOD (DeepSeek)</i>			
BioClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.798	0.814	0.758
ClinicalBERT (baseline)	0.811	0.821	0.768
PubMedBERT (baseline)	0.913	0.886	0.846
BlueBERT (baseline)	0.854	0.852	0.841
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	0.988	0.971	0.969
ClinicalBERT (CL)	0.983	0.970	0.964
PubMedBERT (CL)	0.999	0.966	0.952
BlueBERT (CL)	0.996	0.959	0.946

4.4 Classification Ablation Study

Based on the results in Table 3, we observe that Logistic Regression is consistently performant across all four contrastively tuned biomedical encoders for both the ID and OOD datasets. This suggests that the sentence representations produced by the contrastively trained encoders are largely linearly separable, making more complex nonlinear models unnecessary in many cases.

Logistic Regression achieves the highest ID F1 score for one of four encoders (BlueBERT) and yields strong OOD generalization performance across all encoders, remaining within a narrow margin of the best-performing classifier in each case. For BioClinicalBERT and ClinicalBERT, Logistic Regression performs comparably to the MLP on ID data (ID F1 = 0.904 vs. 0.912 for BioClinicalBERT; 0.913 vs. 0.920 for ClinicalBERT) while maintaining similar or stronger OOD performance. In contrast, for PubMedBERT, the MLP slightly outperforms Logistic Regression on both ID (0.939 vs. 0.938) and OOD (0.807 vs. 0.785) datasets. A similar pattern is observed for BlueBERT, where the MLP marginally exceeds Logistic Regression on ID performance (0.926 vs. 0.925), while Logistic Regression maintains slightly stronger OOD generalization (0.729 vs. 0.712).

These trends largely persist when evaluating on the HCP-verified datasets. Across encoders, Logistic Regression consistently achieves strong HCP-ID and HCP-OOD performance, remaining close to or outperforming nonlinear alternatives in most cases. Notably, for BlueBERT and PubMedBERT, Logistic Regression attains the highest or near-highest HCP-ID F1 scores (0.826 and 0.815, respectively) and maintains robust performance under distribution shift in the HCP-OOD setting. While MLPs occasionally achieve marginally higher HCP-ID performance for certain encoders, Logistic Regression generally exhibits more stable behavior across both HCP-ID and HCP-OOD evaluations, reinforcing its suitability for guideline-consistency classification under limited labeled data conditions.

Across all eight ID and OOD comparisons, Logistic Regression is either the top-performing or second-best classifier in seven cases, while the MLP achieves the highest F1 score in four cases, primarily on ID data. Random Forest and RBF-kernel SVM models underperform relative to linear and shallow nonlinear models, particularly under distribution shift. For example, Random Forest OOD F1 scores are consistently lower than those of Logistic Regression by approximately 0.10–0.19 across encoders, while RBF SVMs exhibit similar degradation.

This degradation under distribution shift likely reflects overfitting to the ID embedding distribution by more complex nonlinear models, whereas Logistic Regression provides a more stable decision boundary. While further hyperparameter optimization could potentially improve nonlinear model performance, these results indicate that Logistic Regression and shallow MLPs offer the most favorable balance between performance and stability.

Overall, the ablation study demonstrates that once the embedding space has been optimized through contrastive learning, relatively simple linear classifiers are sufficient for downstream safe–unsafe classification, offering strong performance and improved generalization.

Table 3 Classifier ablation results. Metrics reported for contrastively (CL) fine-tuned encoders, as well as In-Distribution (ID) F1, Out-of-Distribution (OOD) F1, and HCP-Verified (HCP) F1.

Encoder	Classifier	ID	OOD	HCP-ID	HCP-OOD
BioClinicalBERT (CL)	Logistic Regression	0.904	0.675	0.776	0.696
	MLP (128-64)	0.912	0.647	0.772	0.686
	Random Forest	0.856	0.487	0.709	0.572
	SVM (RBF)	0.891	0.553	0.732	0.604
ClinicalBERT (CL)	Logistic Regression	0.913	0.695	0.761	0.719
	MLP (128-64)	0.920	0.702	0.749	0.719
	Random Forest	0.864	0.572	0.692	0.558
	SVM (RBF)	0.895	0.604	0.728	0.635
PubMedBERT (CL)	Logistic Regression	0.938	0.785	0.815	0.760
	MLP (128-64)	0.939	0.807	0.802	0.741
	Random Forest	0.921	0.709	0.776	0.697
	SVM (RBF)	0.932	0.709	0.789	0.693
BlueBERT (CL)	Logistic Regression	0.925	0.729	0.826	0.725
	MLP (128-64)	0.926	0.712	0.806	0.710
	Random Forest	0.886	0.585	0.766	0.634
	SVM (RBF)	0.900	0.618	0.786	0.641

4.5 Summary of Results

Overall, the findings from the classification experiments, difficulty-stratified analyses, embedding visualizations, and classifier ablation study demonstrate that contrastive fine-tuning significantly enhances the separability of safe and unsafe LLM-generated clinical statements in their embedding space. Across all metrics, contrastively tuned encoders yield improvements for both ID, OOD, and HCP-verified settings, indicating robustness to paraphrasing and cross-model variation. The t-SNE projections reinforce these results by illustrating embedding space structure and reduced overlap between safe and unsafe classes following contrastive learning. Moreover, the ablation study shows that a simple linear classifier is sufficient to leverage these improved representations, classifying guideline-inconsistent statements more effectively than more complex nonlinear models. Altogether, these results highlight contrastive fine-tuning as an effective and practical strategy for improving the reliability of downstream safety classification in medical LLM outputs.

5 Conclusion

With the advent of new generative AI technologies, the study and application of LLMs in medical contexts has become an increasingly popular field for researchers and practitioners alike. Beyond the research context, there have been a number of special purpose LLMs developed for medical tasks available as open-source and commercial software. Naturally, the increased application of medical LLMs has raised important questions regarding their overall safety, especially considering that healthcare and medicine are critical areas where safety is paramount.

In this work, we introduced a six-stage pipeline for detecting clinical guideline-inconsistent statements generated by LLMs. Our approach utilizes authoritative guideline sources to construct an assumed canonical set of safe treatment statements, paraphrases these statements to model linguistic variation, and synthesizes corresponding unsafe variants with well-defined levels of distortion (easy, medium, and hard). Our results demonstrated that contrastive learning using LLM-generated statement pairs can meaningfully improve the separability of guideline-consistent and guideline-inconsistent statements in embedding space, making it a useful preprocessing step before supervised classification. For four biomedical encoders—BioClinicalBERT, ClinicalBERT, PubMedBERT, and BlueBERT—contrastively fine-tuned models showed clear performance gains over baseline embeddings on the downstream safety classification task. Importantly, this finding is especially true for more difficult (i.e., hard) unsafe variants, where the magnitude of classification performance gain is largest.

An interesting finding of this study is that the applied method performs well on data beyond the LLM used to generate the training data. Classifiers trained on in-distribution (GPT-4o) unsafe statements maintained strong performance on unseen paraphrases and, importantly, on out-of-distribution (DeepSeek) unsafe generations. While exact numerical metrics vary across encoders and difficulty levels, contrastively fine-tuned models consistently outperformed baseline models by substantial margins in AUC, F1 score, and average precision. These results highlight that embeddings trained with explicit guideline-anchored contrastive signals are more robust to lexical shifts, phrasing differences, and model-specific idiosyncrasies.

This study is intended as a proof-of-concept rather than a fully developed clinical safety solution. The dataset used here is small, focused on a single treatment (remdesivir), and relies on synthetic unsafe variants rather than naturally occurring guideline violations. Nonetheless, the results justify the broader claim that structured guideline-based contrastive learning is a viable and effective strategy for detecting unsafe or guideline-inconsistent treatment recommendations. The modular nature of the classification pipeline allows it to be readily extended to additional treatments, diseases, and guideline sets, as well as integrated with more advanced LLM evaluators. In a practical setting, an improved pipeline of this design could be easily implemented for sentence-wise evaluation for every mainstream treatment available for, such as in our case, COVID-19. Overall, it could be a useful addition to other tests that measure LLM safety in the healthcare context.

It should be noted that this work has several limitations. First, this study serves as a proof-of-concept for our specific classification pipeline, as the transformer and classification models in this study are trained on a relatively narrow classification task (remdesivir in the context of COVID-19 treatment recommendations). Second, it is assumed that the corpus of scraped treatment guidelines are indeed canonical, and that there is a level of variability between any given RAG run. Third, it was noted that some guidelines, which are technically correct in some medical contexts, would not necessarily apply to others. This is a natural consequence of the sources being primarily selected for their medical authority rather than strict consistency for remdesivir treatment of COVID-19 (e.g., some recommendations differ for outpatient and inpatient settings). The current construction of the RAG step in the pipeline makes no

distinction between these settings. Fourth, the pipeline in its current form is relatively inefficient in its generation of synthetic statements. No optimization between number of synthetic samples (i.e., positive paraphrases and their negative counterparts) and performance of the embedding models and downstream classifiers was performed. Current generation rules (e.g., 20 paraphrases with 5 negatives each) were largely selected based on trial-and-error. Fifth, due to scope and time constraints, this study does not include evaluation on a large clinician-labeled dataset. Ideally, an LLM could be evaluated under adversarial or corrupted conditions (e.g., via poisoned weights or RAG corpora), with subsequent outputs manually labeled by a team of healthcare experts.

Future work should expand the dataset to include multiple therapeutic areas (including the remainder of recommended COVID-19 treatments), incorporate clinician-labeled and/or naturally occurring unsafe statements, and explore hybrid architectures that combine contrastive embeddings with generative critique models or knowledge graphs. Furthermore, possible future implementations should augment the pipeline to make granular distinctions between care settings. Additional research should also investigate how frequently updated clinical guidelines, multi-lingual settings, or uncertainty-aware classifiers affect performance in real-world deployments or could be used to continuously improve and benchmark medical LLMs.

Overall, the results presented here demonstrate that contrastive learning, trained on synthetic text grounded in authoritative clinical guideline content, offers a scalable and straightforward pathway for improving the safety of medical LLM systems by automatically testing their output against established clinical guidelines. As LLMs continue to be integrated into healthcare workflows, such methods will play an increasingly important role in ensuring that automated recommendations remain aligned with established clinical best practices.

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Declarations

- **Funding** This research received no external funding.
- **Conflict of interest/Competing interests** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.
- **Ethics approval and consent to participate** Ethics approval was not required for this study. The research did not involve human subjects, human data, or human biological material. The licensed healthcare practitioner involved in verification of guideline statements participated in an advisory capacity and did not provide personal or sensitive data.
- **Data availability** The datasets supporting the conclusions of this article will be made publicly available in a GitHub repository upon publication. A persistent identifier and hyperlink will be provided in the final version of the manuscript.
- **Materials availability** Not applicable.
- **Code availability** The code used to generate synthetic data, train embedding models, and evaluate classifiers will be made publicly available in a GitHub repository upon publication.

- **Author contribution** R.B. designed the study, implemented the methodology, conducted the experiments, and drafted the manuscript. P.U. contributed to study design, experiment prototyping, and manuscript revision. Z.D. contributed to data labeling, expert input, and manuscript revision. G.K. contributed to study design.

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